

**THE IMPACT OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ON BUSINESS DECISION-
MAKING**

¹ **Omar Ashurbaev** - author; Senior lecturer, Department of Business Management,
Millat Umidi International University in Tashkent

Email Address: omar.ashur@icloud.com

² **Madinabonu Qurbonova** – co-author; Student of Millat Umidi University; Business
Management faculty (Pearson BTEC)

Abstract: *The following article focuses on the ways how artificial intelligence is transforming business decisions. Here we explore how the various AI technologies such as machine learning, deep learning, and natural language processing, are impacting the strategic, tactical and operational decision-making across various industries and fields. That is why the study includes the benefits – improved data analysis, enhanced prediction, and removal of repetitive activities – and the drawbacks – data prejudice, ethical issues, and need for human intervention. The final part of the article under discussion is devoted to the fact that the involvement of people in AI decision-making process is evolving and provides the possible directions for the future research.*

Key words: predictive modelling and analysis, including algorithms, big data, advanced data analytics, artificial intelligence, ML, and DL, NLP, business data analytics, business intelligence, business analytics and decision science, AI, data science and analytics, and AI applications in business decisions.

INTRODUCTION

Technological change, particularly in the application of artificial intelligence is becoming extremely fast and is disturbing intensely the commercial field. AI is a tangible and real phenomenon that is altering the very fabric and operation of businesses across the organizations to make critical decisions; the hype is now reality. AI is evident in the organization across the competitive landscape, with implications for market forecasting, supply chain management, more personalized customer experience, and frequent automatization of such complex processes. This article argues that while the use of artificial intelligence (AI) has never been more valuable aiding in effective business decisions through analyzing data and predictive capabilities that could not be done before, it must also say that a successful use of this form of technology requires reviewing the ethical issues, the limitations of the data and a rigorous reconsideration of the work of the human intellect in managing the business environment.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In recent years, there is much attention paid to how the use of artificial intelligence can influence managerial decision-making process. Increasing attention has been paid to examine both the opportunity of AI as well as the challenges that come along with it. AI is indeed transforming a number of business tasks, such as predictive analytics, operational effectiveness, and decision-making processes at different levels of the organization and this literature review comprises of previous research on the topic.

DECISION SUPPORT SYSTEMS AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN BUSINESS

Consequently, used in company decision making and increasing organizational performance, the AI tools most often applied these days are machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL), as well as natural language processing (NLP). Studies also show that in functional applications such as sales forecast, credit risk evaluation, and customer attrition rate estimation, machine learning methods—more specifically, predictive analytics—outperform traditional statistical methods (Chen et al, 2020).

These developments enable firms to capture large quantity data that would have been difficult to obtain systematically hence enabling intelligent decisions to be made.

AI has demonstrated its capability to handle drudges; improve operations; and speed up decision-making across the tactical and operational levels. For example, it has been shown that the use of AI-based PM for the manufacturing industries significantly reduces expected downtime and enhances working productivity (Lee et al., 2018). Also, AI-based CRM systems can reduce customer service, as well as provide personalized services that will enhance the satisfaction of the customer (Davenport et al., 2020).

NATURAL LANGUAGE PROCESSING AND DEEP LEARNING

One of the subcategories of machine learning, deep learning, has added to AI's ability to analyze complex, self-organized information. DL models excel in speech-to-text systems, picture recognition and NLP including automatic translation services and prediction of sentiments. For the same reason as it can look for trends in huge datasets containing information about transactions that can point at a fraudulent nature of the action, DL is particularly useful in business as a tool for fraud detection (Li et al., 2019). Besides, NLP makes it easier for organizations to evaluate information they gather from clients via social media, reviews, and call center records in the process of establishing appropriate marketing strategies and products (Hu et al., 2021).

ADOPTION CHALLENGES FOR AI

However, there are several challenges faced when intending to incorporate AI into business decision-making process. Of greatest concern is data bias that leads to prejudice of similar kind in the outcome if the training data contained prejudice or discrimination of certain groups. In the similar studies, it was found that such data biases can produce AI models that perpetrate current social inequities and more so in sensitive areas such as policing, credit granting, and hiring. For instance, skewed data means that such things as discriminating against minorities then practicing unfair economics can occur.

Opacity of other AI decision-making processes is another big problem and it becomes even worse if the AI is based on complex structures such as deep learning models where the internal logic of the AI decision-making process is rather described as a 'black box' than as a transparent structure. The discussed opacity gives rise to such issues of trust and responsibility in AI systems. Need for more interpretable models According to Ribeiro and colleagues, research on explainable AI (XAI) requires the design of more models, which directors and companies can understand the rationale for their actions. It has also been established that if there are transparency issues, businesses can be averse to mainly relying on AI or relying on the outputs of the AI for critical business decisions.

Moreover, adopting AI in business requires significant resources required in capturing data, people infrastructure. The cost and resource availability of AI are the significant issues in the context of AI for small organizations especially present challenges that severely limit their ability to harness AI. Hence, research conducted by Brynjolfsson and McAfee (2014) reveals that the cost in relation to implementing the use of AI is costly and this indicates that companies have to realize the importance of engaging in what can be termed as AI Grand Strategy, these considerations will depend on the culture of the organizations as well as the overall skill set of its workforce.

METHODOLOGY

This article adopts a conceptual framework that examines the impact of AI on business decision-making across three levels:

Strategic Decision-Making: This means strategic actions that involve the organization's ideals, directions, positioning for market share, and the deployment of resources. In this area, AI can provide the following helpful features: market analysis to define trends and also to predict competitors' actions, search for new opportunities for the growth.

Tactical Decision-Making: This includes decisions at the middle management level that is involved with actualization of strategic plans and objectives. It goes without saying that AI can improve or enhance several processes including inventory, supply chain, and marketing.

Operational Decision-Making: They entail minor, routine choices about manufacturing processes, relations with customers or behaviors within the organization. AI can apply itself to simple automate processes, be timesaving, and increase customer satisfaction.

The paper incorporates secondary materials into the discussion to support how AI is deploying at every level of decision-making.

RESULTS/FINDINGS

In a case of primary research, we used online questionnaires. The reason for designing our survey was the potential of artificial intelligence or AI to influence firm-level decision-making and the opportunities and constraints that surround its application. The respondents of the survey were professionals and students, people between 18 to 45 years old with a specific focus on Uzbek respondents. From the survey, 55 participants responded to the survey.

The survey objectives were to assess the understanding of organizations about AI technologies, how far they have used these technologies, and the issues of ethicality of their use. In analyzing the responses, it was possible to analyze common trends, advantages, as well as main challenges that affect AI implementation in businesses. **The survey questions included the following:**

1. *How much do you know about Artificial Intelligence or AI technologies?*
2. *Is AI incorporated in your organization today?*
3. *Where are you using AI most intensively in your business?*
4. *What positive impact has the implementation of AI in your organization delivered?*
5. *What problems have you encountered when integrating AI technologies?*
6. *What was your understanding about the part human decision-making plays in AI algorithms?*
7. *What is your opinion on AI in ethical dilemmas relating to business decision making?*

8. *What do you think is needed in order to preserve ethical and efficient AI in business?*

Q1: Familiarity with AI Technologies

Q3: Areas of Business Where AI is Utilized

- A clear majority 81.9% answered in the affirmative indicating a reasonable level of awareness amongst the subjects sampled.

- Half of the respondents said their organization deploys AI, but a significant proportion either don't or are unsure.

- Ethical issues are a major concern for most people meaning that there are so many issues which need to be addressed in the specific area as relates to bias, fairness, and accountability in Artificial Intelligence applications.

Thus, the survey conclusions establish high global AI awareness and utilization, as well as the problems which persist in the form of ethical issues and the adoption that remains more or less half-complete.

DISCUSSION

The outcomes presented shed light on one of the key benefits of the AI approach to decision-making within a business environment. Due to the big amounts of data available, as well as decision making support tools, AI helps businesses to make the right decision. However, there are some points that have to be noticed as mere limitations of AI where some risks are also followed afterwards. This issue means that decisions made through machine learning will have unfair or even discriminating judgment given the bias nature of the data collected through the algorithmed information transactions.

For AI integration to work, it has to be largely human-focused. AI offers particular ways of changing low-skill work or providing basic data analysis but it cannot replace human judgment to tackle complex situations, interpret the AI generated information, and ensure that ethical issues are taken into account. A human is no longer passive participant or only a decision maker but he or she is an active participant in cooperation with AI. This is where we have to make sure we have the right people that will be in a position to comprehend AI readouts and regulate them.

CONCLUSION

AI is proving that it's revolutionizing the nature of business decisions. Its capacity to discern large data sets, pattern recognition, and the ability to predict the future provides clear and compelling benefits for organizations of virtually any kind. However, to achieve the maximal benefit of AI, the issues and threats regarding data prejudice, data openness, and utilization of ethical principles must be solved. Business decision making in the future will involve a

combination of human and AI decision making to harness on the strengths of both systems in making good, accountable, and transformational decisions.

Future research should focus on several key areas: In general, expanding on the transparency and interpretability of AI solutions; reducing the risks of AI-generated bias as a result of data preprocessing and algorithm selection; studying employment and the workforce in the context of AI development; and identifying the ethical guidelines and regulatory tools for managing the proper use of AI in decision making. Moreover, attempts at understanding the process of effective implementation of AI in organizations and their environments will be essential for the optimization of the strengths and the minimization of the threats connected with the application of this revolutionary technology. Last but not the least we need more studies towards identifying the change in human – AI partnership model and create programs that prepare the workforce to deal with AI systems.

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